

SUPPORTING INFORMATION: DATA SOURCES

TABLE S3.1. List of studies incorporated into both the nuclear (microsatellite) and mitochondrial DNA datasets. For mitochondrial DNA, all studies reported both H_d and π unless otherwise specified. References are provided after the table.

Family	Species	Common name	nuclear	mitochondrial	References
Pomacentridae	<i>Abudefduf saxatilis</i>	Sergeant-major	X	X	Piñeros <i>et al.</i> (2015) ^a ; Piñeros <i>et al.</i> (2015) ^b ; Piñeros & Gutiérrez-Rodríguez (2017)
Pomacentridae	<i>Acanthochromis polyacanthus</i>	Spiny chromis	X		Miller-Sims <i>et al.</i> (2005) ^a ; Miller-Sims <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Scombridae	<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i>	Wahoo		X	Garber <i>et al.</i> (2005)
Sparidae	<i>Acanthopagrus australis</i>	Yellowfin bream	X		Roberts & Ayre (2010)
Sparidae	<i>Acanthopagrus berda</i>	Goldsilk seabream	X		Jean <i>et al.</i> (2006); Tseng <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Sparidae	<i>Acanthopagrus latus</i>	Yellowfin seabream	X		Ghasemi & Shadi (2018)
Sparidae	<i>Acanthopagrus schlegelii</i>	Blackhead seabream	X	X	An <i>et al.</i> (2010); Jean <i>et al.</i> (1998); Jeong <i>et al.</i> (2003); Kim <i>et al.</i> (2010) ^a ; Liu <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Sparidae	<i>Acanthopagrus taiwanensis</i>	Taiwan picnic seabream	X		Tseng <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Acanthuridae	<i>Acanthurus leucosternon</i>	Powder blue surgeonfish	X		DiBattista <i>et al.</i> (2011) ^a ; Otwoma <i>et al.</i> (2018) ^a
Acanthuridae	<i>Acanthurus nigricans</i>	Whitecheek surgeonfish	X		DiBattista <i>et al.</i> (2011) ^a
Acanthuridae	<i>Acanthurus nigrofuscus</i>	Brown surgeonfish		X	Eble <i>et al.</i> (2011) ^a

Acanthuridae	<i>Acanthurus nigroris</i>	Bluelined surgeonfish		X	DiBattista <i>et al.</i> (2011) ^b
Acanthuridae	<i>Acanthurus triostegus</i>	Convict surgeonfish	X	X	Otwoma <i>et al.</i> (2018) ^b ; Otwoma & Reuter (2019)
Myliobatidae	<i>Aetobatus narinari</i>	Spotted eagle ray	X	X	Sellas <i>et al.</i> (2011); Sellas <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Alopiidae	<i>Alopias vulpinus</i>	Thresher		X	Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Rajidae	<i>Amblyraja radiata</i>	Starry ray		X	Chevolot <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Ammodytidae	<i>Ammodytes personatus</i>	Pacific sandlance	X	X	Deng <i>et al.</i> (2019); Kim <i>et al.</i> (2006); Ren <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Pomacentridae	<i>Amphiprion akallopisos</i>	Skunk clownfish	X	X	Huyghe & Kochzius (2018); O'Donnell <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Pomacentridae	<i>Amphiprion clarkii</i>	Yellowtail clownfish	X		Pinsky <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Pomacentridae	<i>Amphiprion frenatus</i>	Tomato clownfish	X		Sato <i>et al.</i> (2014); Sato <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Pomacentridae	<i>Amphiprion latezonatus</i>	Wide-band anemonefish		X	Steinberg <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Pomacentridae	<i>Amphiprion mccullochi</i>	Whitesnout anemonefish	X		van der Meer <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Pomacentridae	<i>Amphiprion melanopus</i>	Fire clownfish	X	X (π)	Bonin <i>et al.</i> (2016); Drew <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Pomacentridae	<i>Amphiprion ocellaris</i>	Clown anemonefish	X		Madduppa <i>et al.</i> (2014); Timm <i>et al.</i> (2012); Timm <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Pomacentridae	<i>Amphiprion percula</i>	Orange clownfish	X		Bonin <i>et al.</i> (2016); Buston <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Pomacentridae	<i>Amphiprion perideraion</i>	Pink anemonefish	X		Donha <i>et al.</i> (2015); Madduppa <i>et al.</i> (2014); Sato <i>et al.</i> (2014); Sato <i>et al.</i> (2017)

Pomacentridae	<i>Amphiprion polymnus</i>	Saddleback clownfish	X		Saenz-Agudelo <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Anarhichadidae	<i>Anarhichas lupus</i>	Atlantic wolffish	X		McCusker & Bentzen (2010); Pampoulie <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Anoplopomatidae	<i>Anoplopoma fimbria</i>	Sablefish	X	X	Tripp-Valdez <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Moridae	<i>Antimora rostrata</i>	Blue antimoral	X		White <i>et al.</i> (2011) ^a
Trichiuridae	<i>Aphanopus carbo</i>	Black scabbardfish	X		Knutsen <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Trichiuridae	<i>Aphanopus intermedius</i>	Intermediate scabbardfish	X		Knutsen <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Gobiidae	<i>Aphia minuta</i>	Transparent goby	X		Ruggeri <i>et al.</i> (2016) ^a
Apogonidae	<i>Apogon imberbis</i>	Cardinal fish	X		Galarza <i>et al.</i> (2007) ^a ; Galarza <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^a ; Muths <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Sparidae	<i>Archosargus probatocephalus</i>	Sheepshead		X (π)	Seyoum <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Sciaenidae	<i>Argyrosomus coronus</i>	Dusky kob	X		Henriques <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Sciaenidae	<i>Argyrosomus inodorus</i>	Mild meagre	X		Henriques <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Sciaenidae	<i>Argyrosomus japonicus</i>	Japanese meagre	X		Barnes <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Sciaenidae	<i>Argyrosomus regius</i>	Meagre	X		Haffray <i>et al.</i> (2012); Porta <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Atherinopsidae	<i>Atherinella brasiliensis</i>	Brazilian silverside		X	da Silva Cortinhas <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Sciaenidae	<i>Atractoscion aequidens</i>	Geelbeck croaker	X		Henriques <i>et al.</i> (2012) ^a ; Henriques <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Scombridae	<i>Auxis rochei</i>	Bullet tuna		X	Habib & Sulaiman (2016)

Scombridae	<i>Auxis thazard</i>	Frigate tuna		X	Habib & Sulaiman (2016); Kumar <i>et al.</i> (2012) ^a ; Pedrosa-Gerasmio <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Balistidae	<i>Balistes capriscus</i>	Grey triggerfish		X	Antoni <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Gobiidae	<i>Bathygobius cocosensis</i>	Cocos frill-goby		X	Mukai <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Dasyatidae	<i>Bathytoshia centroura</i>	Roughtail stingray		X	Vella <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Rajidae	<i>Beringraja pulchra</i>	Mottled skate		X	Im <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Tripterygiidae	<i>Bellapiscis lesleyae</i>	Mottled twister		X	Hickey <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Tripterygiidae	<i>Bellapiscis medius</i>	Twister		X	Hickey <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Berycidae	<i>Beryx decadactylus</i>	Alfonsino		X	Friess & Sedberry (2011)
Berycidae	<i>Beryx splendens</i>	Splendid alfonsino		X	Lévy-Hartmann <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Gadidae	<i>Boreogadus saida</i>	Polar cod	X	X	Madsen <i>et al.</i> (2016); Pálsson <i>et al.</i> (2009); Wilson <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Malacanthidae	<i>Branchiostegus japonicus</i>	Horsehead tilefish		X	Nohara <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^a
Branchiostomati dae	<i>Branchiostoma belcheri</i>	NA		X	Li <i>et al.</i> (2013) ^a
Branchiostomati dae	<i>Branchiostoma japonicum</i>	NA		X	Li <i>et al.</i> (2013) ^a
Clupeidae	<i>Brevoortia gunteri</i>	Finescale menhaden	X		Anderson & Karel (2007); Anderson & McDonald (2007); Lynch (2008)
Clupeidae	<i>Brevoortia patronus</i>	Gulf menhaden	X		Anderson & Karel (2007); Anderson & McDonald (2007); Lynch (2010)
Clupeidae	<i>Brevoortia smithi</i>	Yellowfin menhaden	X		Anderson & Karel (2014); Lynch (2008)

Clupeidae	<i>Brevoortia tyrannus</i>	Atlantic menhaden	X		Anderson & Karel (2007); Lynch <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Lotidae	<i>Brosme brosme</i>	Cusk	X		Knutsen <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Gobiidae	<i>Caffrogobius caffer</i>	NA		X	Neethling <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Carcharhinidae	<i>Carcharhinus albimarginatus</i>	Silvertip shark	X		Green <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Carcharhinidae	<i>Carcharhinus amblyrhynchos</i>	Gray reef shark	X		Boissin <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Carcharhinidae	<i>Carcharhinus galapagensis</i>	Galapagos shark		X	Pazmiño <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Carcharhinidae	<i>Carcharhinus isodon</i>	Finetooth shark	X		Portnoy <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Carcharhinidae	<i>Carcharhinus leucas</i>	Bull shark	X		Pirog <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Carcharhinidae	<i>Carcharhinus limbatus</i>	Blacktip shark	X		Almojil <i>et al.</i> (2018); Keeney <i>et al.</i> (2005)
Carcharhinidae	<i>Carcharhinus signatus</i>	Night shark	X		Domingues <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Carcharhinidae	<i>Carcharhinus sorrah</i>	Spot-tail shark	X		Almojil <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Carcharhinidae	<i>Carcharias taurus</i>	Sand tiger shark	X		Feldheim <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Lamnidae	<i>Carcharodon carcharias</i>	Great white shark	X	X	Andreotti <i>et al.</i> (2016); Blower <i>et al.</i> (2012); Pardini <i>et al.</i> (2000)
Centrophoridae	<i>Centrophorus harrissoni</i>	Dumb gulper shark		X (π)	Daley <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Centrophoridae	<i>Centrophorus moluccensis</i>	Smallfin gulper shark		X (π)	Daley <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Centrophoridae	<i>Centrophorus uyato</i>	Little gulper shark		X	Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Centrophoridae	<i>Centrophorus zeehaani</i>	Southern dogfish		X (π)	Daley <i>et al.</i> (2012)

Serranidae	<i>Centropristis striata</i>	Black seabass		X	Roy <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Somniosidae	<i>Centroscymnus crepidater</i>	Longnose velvet dogfish	X	X	Cunha <i>et al.</i> (2012); Helyar <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Serranidae	<i>Cephalopholis argus</i>	Peacock hind		X	Gaither <i>et al.</i> (2011) ^a ; Gaither <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Serranidae	<i>Cephalopholis fulva</i>	Coney	X	X	De Souza <i>et al.</i> (2015); Renshaw <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Engraulidae	<i>Cetengraulis edentulous</i>	Atlantic anchoveta		X (<i>H_d</i>)	Grant <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Chaetodontidae	<i>Chaenocephalus aceratus</i>	Blackfin icefish	X		Damerau <i>et al.</i> (2012); Damerau <i>et al.</i> (2014) ^a ; Papetti <i>et al.</i> (2007); Susana <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Chaetodontidae	<i>Chaetodon austriacus</i>	Blacktail butterflyfish		X	Waldrop <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Chaetodontidae	<i>Chaetodon lunulatus</i>	Oval butterflyfish	X	X	Lawton <i>et al.</i> (2010); Lawton <i>et al.</i> (2011); Montanari <i>et al.</i> (2011); Waldrop <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Chaetodontidae	<i>Chaetodon melapterus</i>	Arabian butterflyfish		X	Waldrop <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Chaetodontidae	<i>Chaetodon meyeri</i>	Scrawled butterflyfish		X	DiBattista <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Chaetodontidae	<i>Chaetodon multicinctus</i>	Pebbled butterflyfish	X		Heist <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Chaetodontidae	<i>Chaetodon ornatissimus</i>	Ornate butterflyfish		X	DiBattista <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Chaetodontidae	<i>Chaetodon tricinctus</i>	Three-striped butterflyfish	X	X	van der Meer <i>et al.</i> (2013) ^a
Chaetodontidae	<i>Chaetodon trifasciatus</i>	Melon butterflyfish	X	X	Lawton <i>et al.</i> (2010); Lawton <i>et al.</i> (2011); Montanari <i>et al.</i> (2011); Waldrop <i>et al.</i> (2016)

Channichthyidae	<i>Champscephalus gunnari</i>	Mackerel icefish	X		Damerou <i>et al.</i> (2012); Damerou <i>et al.</i> (2014) ^a ; Young <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Labridae	<i>Cheilinus undulatus</i>	Humphead wrasse	X		Hu <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Apogonidae	<i>Cheilodipterus artus</i>	Wolf cardinalfish	X		Underwood (2010)
Channichthyidae	<i>Chionodraco rastrispinosus</i>	Ocellated icefish	X		Damerou <i>et al.</i> (2012); Papetti <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Pomacentridae	<i>Chromis margaritifer</i>	Bicolor chromis	X		Underwood (2009); Underwood <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Pomacentridae	<i>Chromis multilineata</i>	Brown chromis		X	Rocha <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Pomacentridae	<i>Chromis viridis</i>	Blue green damselfish		X	Liu <i>et al.</i> (2019) ^a
Pomacentridae	<i>Chrysiptera talboti</i>	Talbot's demoiselle		X (π)	Drew <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Sparidae	<i>Chrysoblephus laticeps</i>	Roman seabream	X	X	Teske <i>et al.</i> (2009); Teske <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Sparidae	<i>Chrysoblephus puniceus</i>	Slinger seabream	X	X	Chopelet <i>et al.</i> (2009); Duncan <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Labridae	<i>Cirrhilabrus punctatus</i>	Dotted wrasse		X (π)	Drew <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Pleuronectidae	<i>Cleisthenes herzensteini</i>	Sôhachi		X	Xiao <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Clupeidae	<i>Clupea harengus</i>	Atlantic herring	X		Bekkevold <i>et al.</i> (2005); Bekkevold <i>et al.</i> (2016); Jørgensen <i>et al.</i> (2005) ^a ; Jørgensen <i>et al.</i> (2005) ^b ; Larsson <i>et al.</i> (2010); Mariani <i>et al.</i> (2005); McPherson <i>et al.</i> (2001) ^a ; McPherson <i>et al.</i> (2001) ^b ; Pampoulie <i>et al.</i> (2015); Shaw <i>et al.</i> (1999); Teacher <i>et al.</i> (2013); Wennerström <i>et al.</i> (2013)

Clupeidae	<i>Clupea pallasii pallasii</i>	Pacific herring	X	X	Beacham <i>et al.</i> (2001); Grant <i>et al.</i> (2012); Mitchell (2006); O'Connell <i>et al.</i> (1998) ^a ; O'Connell <i>et al.</i> (1998) ^b ; Olsen <i>et al.</i> (2002); Semenova <i>et al.</i> (2015); Semenova <i>et al.</i> (2018); Small <i>et al.</i> (2005); Wildes <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Sciaenidae	<i>Collichthys lucidus</i>	Spinyhead croaker		X	Xiao <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Congridae	<i>Conger conger</i>	European conger		X	Correia <i>et al.</i> (2006); Correia <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Labridae	<i>Coris bulbifrons</i>	Doubleheader	X	X	van der Meer <i>et al.</i> (2013) ^a ; van der Meer <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Labridae	<i>Coris julis</i>	Mediterranean rainbow wrasse	X		Guillemaud <i>et al.</i> (2000)
Coryphaenidae	<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>	Common dolphinfish	X		Tripp-Valdez <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Macrouridae	<i>Coryphaenoides armatus</i>	Abyssal grenadier	X		Ritchie <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Macrouridae	<i>Coryphaenoides brevibarbis</i>	Shortbeard grenadier	X		White <i>et al.</i> (2011) ^b
Macrouridae	<i>Coryphaenoides mediterraneus</i>	Mediterranean grenadier	X	X	Catarino <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Liparidae	<i>Crystallias matsushimae</i>	NA		X	Tohkairin <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Labridae	<i>Ctenolabrus rupestris</i>	Goldsinny-wrasse	X		Jansson <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Cyclopteridae	<i>Cyclopterus lumpus</i>	Lumpfish	X		Jónsdóttir <i>et al.</i> (2018); Pampoulie <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Embiotocidae	<i>Cymatogaster aggregata</i>	Shiner perch	X		Liu & Avise (2011)
Cynoglossidae	<i>Cynoglossus semilaevis</i>	Tongue sole	X		Liu <i>et al.</i> (2008); Liu <i>et al.</i> (2011)

Sciaenidae	<i>Cynoscion arenarius</i>	Sand weakfish	X		Anderson <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Sciaenidae	<i>Cynoscion nebulosus</i>	Spotted weakfish	X	X	Anderson & Karel (2009); Anderson & Karel (2010); Renshaw <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^a
Sciaenidae	<i>Cynoscion nothus</i>	Silver seatrout	X		Anderson <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Dalatiidae	<i>Dalatias licha</i>	Kitefin shark		X	Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Pomacentridae	<i>Dascyllus aruanus</i>	Humbug damselfish	X		Liu <i>et al.</i> (2014) ^a ; Pini <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Pomacentridae	<i>Dascyllus strasburgi</i>	Strasburg's dascyllus	X		Leray <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Pomacentridae	<i>Dascyllus trimaculatus</i>	Threespot dascyllus	X		Bernardi <i>et al.</i> (2012); Leray <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Dasyatidae	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	Common stingray		X	Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Sparidae	<i>Dentex dentex</i>	Common dentex	X		Viret <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Myctophidae	<i>Diaphus theta</i>	California headlightfish		X	Kojima <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Moronidae	<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>	European seabass	X	X	Bahri-Sfar <i>et al.</i> (2000); Fritsch <i>et al.</i> (2007); García de León <i>et al.</i> (1997); Lemaire <i>et al.</i> (2005); Naciri <i>et al.</i> (1999)
Sparidae	<i>Diplodus hottentotus</i>	Zebra seabream	X		Gwilliam <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Sparidae	<i>Diplodus sargus</i>	White seabream	X	X	Di Franco <i>et al.</i> (2012); Exadactylos <i>et al.</i> (2019); González-Wangüemert <i>et al.</i> (2010); González-Wangüemert <i>et al.</i> (2011); González-Wangüemert & Pérez-Ruzafa (2012); González-Wangüemert <i>et al.</i> (2012); Kaouèche <i>et al.</i> (2013); Pujolar <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Sparidae	<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i>	Common two-banded	X		Galarza <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^a ; Roques <i>et al.</i>

		seabream			(2007); Steffani <i>et al.</i> (2015); Sahyoun <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Rajidae	<i>Dipturus oxyrinchus</i>	Longnosed skate		X	Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Rajidae	<i>Dipturus trachyderma</i>	Roughskin skate	X	X	Vargas-Caro <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Nototheniidae	<i>Dissostichus eleginoides</i>	Patagonian toothfish	X		Appleyard <i>et al.</i> (2004); Arenada <i>et al.</i> (2017); Garcia <i>et al.</i> (2019); Reilly & Ward (1999); Rogers <i>et al.</i> (2006); Shaw <i>et al.</i> (2004); Smith & McVeagh (2000)
Myctophidae	<i>Electrona antarctica</i>	Antarctica lanternfish	X		Valenzuela-Quiñonez (2014); Van de Putte <i>et al.</i> (2012) ^a
Eleginopsidae	<i>Eleginops maclovinus</i>	Patagonian blennie	X	X	Ceballos <i>et al.</i> (2012); Ceballos <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Elopidae	<i>Elops saurus</i>	Ladyfish	X		Sha <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Embiotocidae	<i>Embiotoca jacksoni</i>	Black perch	X		Bernardi (2008)
Engraulidae	<i>Engraulis australis</i>	Australian anchovy	X	X	Silva <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Engraulidae	<i>Engraulis capensis</i>	Southern African anchovy	X	X	Silva <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Engraulidae	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	European anchovy	X	X	Borrell <i>et al.</i> (2012); Ouazzani <i>et al.</i> (2017); Pakaki <i>et al.</i> (2009); Ruggeri <i>et al.</i> (2016) ^b ; Silva <i>et al.</i> (2014); Viñas <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Engraulidae	<i>Engraulis eurystole</i>	Silver anchovy	X	X	Silva <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Engraulidae	<i>Engraulis japonicus</i>	Japanese anchovy	X	X	Chen <i>et al.</i> (2010); Lin <i>et al.</i> (2011); Liu <i>et al.</i> (2006); Silva <i>et al.</i> (2017); Yu <i>et al.</i> (2002); Yu <i>et al.</i> (2005); Zheng <i>et al.</i>

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Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus akaara</i>	Hong Kong grouper	X	X	Chen <i>et al.</i> (2008); Koedprang <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus awoara</i>	Yellow grouper	X		Zhao <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^a
Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus bleekeri</i>	Duskytail grouper	X		Koedprang <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus bruneus</i>	Kelp grouper	X		An <i>et al.</i> (2012) ^a ; Kang <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus coioides</i>	Orange-spotted grouper	X		Antoro <i>et al.</i> (2006); Koedprang <i>et al.</i> (2007); Pumitinsee <i>et al.</i> (2009); Wang <i>et al.</i> (2010) ^a
Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus fasciatus</i>	Blacktip grouper		X (<i>H_d</i>)	Kuriiwa <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus guttatus</i>	Red hind	X		Ramírez <i>et al.</i> (2006); Renshaw <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus itajara</i>	Atlantic goliath grouper		X	Craig <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus lanceolatus</i>	Giant grouper	X		Wang <i>et al.</i> (2016); Yang <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus maculatus</i>	Highfin grouper	X		Koedprang <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus malabaricus</i>	Malabar grouper	X		Koedprang <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus marginatus</i>	Dusky grouper	X		Buchholz-Sørensen & Vella (2016); de Innocentiis <i>et al.</i> (2001); Schunter <i>et al.</i> (2011) ^a
Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus merra</i>	Honeycomb grouper	X	X	Koedprang <i>et al.</i> (2007); Matias <i>et al.</i> (2013); Muths & Bourjea (2011)
Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus morio</i>	Red grouper	X		Zatcoff <i>et al.</i> (2004)

Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus ongus</i>	White-streaked grouper	X		Koedprang <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus polyphemadion</i>	Camouflage grouper	X		Ma <i>et al.</i> (2018); Rhodes <i>et al.</i> (2003)
Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus striatus</i>	Nassau grouper	X	X	Jackson <i>et al.</i> (2014); Sherman <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Lutjanidae	<i>Etelis carbunculus</i>	Deep-water red snapper		X	Andrews <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Lutjanidae	<i>Etelis coruscans</i>	Deep-water longtail red snapper		X	Andrews <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Etmopteridae	<i>Etmopterus molleri</i>	Slendertail lanternshark	X		Oury <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Etmopteridae	<i>Etmopterus spinax</i>	Velvet belly	X		Oury <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Gobiidae	<i>Eucyclogobius newberryi</i>	Tidewater goby	X		McCraney <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Scombridae	<i>Euthynnus affinis</i>	Kawakawa		X	Kumar <i>et al.</i> (2012) ^b ; Santos <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Gobiidae	<i>Eviota albolineata</i>	White-line dwarfgoby		X	Farnsworth <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Gobiidae	<i>Eviota queenslandica</i>	Queensland dwarfgoby		X	Farnsworth <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Fistulariidae	<i>Fistularia commersonii</i>	Bluespotted cornetfish		X (<i>H_d</i>)	Golani <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Tripterygiidae	<i>Forsterygion capito</i>	Spotted robust triplefin	X	X	Hickey <i>et al.</i> (2009); Rabone <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Tripterygiidae	<i>Forsterygion gymnotum</i>	Tasmanian robust triplefin		X	Hickey <i>et al.</i> (2009)

Tripterygiidae	<i>Forsterygion lapillum</i>	Common triplefin	X	X	Hickey <i>et al.</i> (2009); Rabone <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Tripterygiidae	<i>Forsterygion nigripenne</i>	Estuarine triplefin		X	Hickey <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Tripterygiidae	<i>Forsterygion varium</i>	Striped triplefin		X	Hickey <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Gadidae	<i>Gadus chalcogrammus</i>	Alaska pollock	X		O'Reilly <i>et al.</i> (2004); Olsen <i>et al.</i> (2002); Shubina <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Gadidae	<i>Gadus macrocephalus</i>	Pacific cod	X	X	Canino <i>et al.</i> (2005); Canino <i>et al.</i> (2010); Cunningham (2007); Cunningham <i>et al.</i> (2009); Gwak & Nakayama (2011); Kim <i>et al.</i> (2010) ^b ; Liu <i>et al.</i> (2010) ^a ; Song <i>et al.</i> (2016); Spies (2012); Stroganov <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Gadidae	<i>Gadus morhua</i>	Atlantic cod	X	X	Bentzen <i>et al.</i> (1996); Bradbury <i>et al.</i> (2009); Carr <i>et al.</i> (1995); Dahle <i>et al.</i> (2018); Karlsson & Monk (2005); Kijewska <i>et al.</i> (2011); Knutsen <i>et al.</i> (2003); Lait <i>et al.</i> (2018); Nielsen <i>et al.</i> (2003); O'Leary <i>et al.</i> (2007); Pampoulie <i>et al.</i> (2006); Poulsen <i>et al.</i> (2006); Ruzzante <i>et al.</i> (1996) ^a ; Ruzzante <i>et al.</i> (1996) ^b ; Ruzzante <i>et al.</i> (1997); Ruzzante <i>et al.</i> (1998); Ruzzante <i>et al.</i> (2000); Ruzzante <i>et al.</i> (2001); Skarstein <i>et al.</i> (2007); Wennevik <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Triakidae	<i>Galeorhinus galeus</i>	School shark	X		Bester-van der Merwe <i>et al.</i> (2017); Maduna <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Scyliorhinidae	<i>Galeus melastomus</i>	Blackmouth catshark		X (<i>H_d</i>)	Ferrari <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Ophidiidae	<i>Genypterus capensis</i>	Kingklip	X	X	Henriques <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Ginglymostomati	<i>Ginglymostoma cirratum</i>	Nurse shark	X	X	Karl <i>et al.</i> (2012); Heist <i>et al.</i> (2003)

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Girellidae	<i>Girella laevisfrons</i>	NA	X		Cerda <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Girellidae	<i>Girella punctata</i>	Largescale blackfish	X	X	Saito <i>et al.</i> (2008); Umino <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Glaucosomatidae	<i>Glaucosoma hebraicum</i>	West Australian dhufish	X		Berry <i>et al.</i> (2012) ^a ; Burrige & England (2009)
Pleuronectidae	<i>Glyptocephalus stelleri</i>	Blackfin flounder		X	Xiao <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Gobiidae	<i>Gnatholepis anjerensis</i>	Eye-bar goby	X		Thacker <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Gobiidae	<i>Gnatholepis cauerensis</i>	Eyebar goby	X		Thacker <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Nototheniidae	<i>Gobionotothen gibberifrons</i>	Humped rockcod	X		Damerou <i>et al.</i> (2012); Matschiner <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Scombridae	<i>Gymnosarda unicolor</i>	Dogtooth tuna	X		Bentley <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Muraenidae	<i>Gymnothorax chilospilus</i>	Lipspot moray	X		Ribout <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Haemulidae	<i>Haemulon flavolineatum</i>	French grunt	X		Purcell <i>et al.</i> (2006); Williams <i>et al.</i> (2004) ^a
Haemulidae	<i>Haemulon plumierii</i>	White grunt	X		O'Donnell <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Labridae	<i>Halichoeres cyanocephalus</i>	Yellowcheek wrasse		X	Rocha (2004)
Labridae	<i>Halichoeres garnoti</i>	Yellowhead wrasse		X	Rocha (2004)
Labridae	<i>Halichoeres maculipinna</i>	Clown wrasse		X	Rocha (2004)
Hapalogenyidae	<i>Hapalogenys nigripinnis</i>	Short barbeled velvetchin	X		An <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Scorpaenidae	<i>Helicolenus dactylopterus</i>	Blackbelly rosefish	X		Aboim <i>et al.</i> (2003)

Hexanchidae	<i>Heptranchias perlo</i>	Sharpnose sevengill shark		X	Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Hexagrammidae	<i>Hexagrammos agrammus</i>	Spotty-bellied greenling		X	Habib <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Hexagrammidae	<i>Hexagrammos otakii</i>	Fat greenling		X	Habib <i>et al.</i> (2011); Ren <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Hexanchidae	<i>Hexanchus griseus</i>	Bluntnose sixgill shark	X	X	Larson <i>et al.</i> (2011); Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Syngnathidae	<i>Hippocampus angustus</i>	Western spiny seahorse	X		Jones <i>et al.</i> (1998) ^a
Syngnathidae	<i>Hippocampus guttulatus</i>	Long-snouted seahorse	X		Pardo <i>et al.</i> (2007); Woodall <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Syngnathidae	<i>Hippocampus hippocampus</i>	Short-snouted seahorse	X	X	Lopez <i>et al.</i> (2010) ^a ; Woodall <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Syngnathidae	<i>Hippocampus ingens</i>	Pacific seahorse		X	Saarman <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Syngnathidae	<i>Hippocampus kuda</i>	Spotted seahorse		X	Goswami <i>et al.</i> (2009); Panithanarak <i>et al.</i> (2010); Teske <i>et al.</i> (2005)
Syngnathidae	<i>Hippocampus mohnikei</i>	Japanese seahorse		X	Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2014) ^a
Syngnathidae	<i>Hippocampus trimaculatus</i>	Longnose seahorse		X	Goswami <i>et al.</i> (2009); Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2014) ^a
Pleuronectidae	<i>Hippoglossus hippoglossus</i>	Atlantic halibut	X		Galindo <i>et al.</i> (2011); McGowan & Reith (1999)
Pleuronectidae	<i>Hippoglossus stenolepis</i>	Pacific halibut	X	X	Drinan <i>et al.</i> (2016); Galindo <i>et al.</i> (2011); Hauser <i>et al.</i> (2006); Nielsen <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Holocentridae	<i>Holocentrus adscensionis</i>	Squirrelfish		X	Bowen <i>et al.</i> (2006)

Trachichthyidae	<i>Hoplostethus atlanticus</i>	Orange roughy	X	X	Carlsson <i>et al.</i> (2011); Coughlan <i>et al.</i> (2010); Varela <i>et al.</i> (2012); Varela <i>et al.</i> (2013); White <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Centrolophidae	<i>Hyperoglyphe antarctica</i>	Bluenose warehou		X	Robinson <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Serranidae	<i>Hypoplectrus nigricans</i>	Black hamlet	X		Puebla <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Serranidae	<i>Hypoplectrus puella</i>	Barred hamlet	X		Puebla <i>et al.</i> (2008); Puebla <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Serranidae	<i>Hyporthodus acanthistius</i>	Rooster hind	X		Beldade <i>et al.</i> (2009); Beldade <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Serranidae	<i>Hyporthodus septemfasciatus</i>	Convict grouper	X		Zhao <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^b
Lamnidae	<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i>	Shortfin mako		X	Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Istiophoridae	<i>Kajikia albida</i>	Atlantic white martin	X		Graves & McDowell (2006); Mamoozadeh <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Pleuronectidae	<i>Kareius bicoloratus</i>	Stone flounder	X		Kim <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^a ; Tian <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Scombridae	<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	Skipjack tuna	X	X	Dammannagoda (2007); Dammannagoda <i>et al.</i> (2011); Menezes <i>et al.</i> (2008); Menezes <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Labridae	<i>Labroides dimidiatus</i>	Bluestreak cleaner wrasse		X	Drew <i>et al.</i> (2008); Sims <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Labridae	<i>Larabicus quadrilineatus</i>	Fourline wrasse		X	Froukh & Kochzius (2007)
Sciaenidae	<i>Larimichthys crocea</i>	Large yellow croaker	X		Guo <i>et al.</i> (2005); Le Wang <i>et al.</i> (2012); Lü <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Sciaenidae	<i>Larimichthys polyactis</i>	Yellow croaker	X	X	Chen <i>et al.</i> (2009); Chen & Cheng (2013); Li <i>et al.</i> (2013) ^b ; Liu <i>et al.</i> (2014) ^b ; Liu <i>et</i>

					<i>al.</i> (2016); Ma <i>et al.</i> (2011) ^a ; Wang <i>et al.</i> (2010) ^b ; Wang <i>et al.</i> (2013); Wang <i>et al.</i> (2015); Xiao <i>et al.</i> (2009); Xiao <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Gobiesocidae	<i>Lepadogaster lepadogaster</i>	Shore clingfish	X		Klein <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Nototheniidae	<i>Lepidonotothen squamifrons</i>	Grey rockcod	X		Damerau <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Scophthalmidae	<i>Lepidorhombus boscii</i>	Four-spotted megrim	X	X	Campo & Garcia-Vazquez (2010); Danancher & Garcia-Vazquez (2009)
Scophthalmidae	<i>Lepidorhombus whiffiagonis</i>	Megrim	X		Danancher & Garcia-Vazquez (2009)
Lethrinidae	<i>Lethrinus harak</i>	Thumbprint emperor	X	X	Healey <i>et al.</i> (2018) ^a
Lethrinidae	<i>Lethrinus laticaudis</i>	Grass emperor	X		Barton <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Lethrinidae	<i>Lethrinus mahsena</i>	Sky emperor	X	X	Healey <i>et al.</i> (2018) ^a
Lethrinidae	<i>Lethrinus miniatus</i>	Trumpet emperor	X		Van Herwerden <i>et al.</i> (2003)
Lethrinidae	<i>Lethrinus nebulosus</i>	Spangled emperor	X	X	Berry <i>et al.</i> (2012) ^b ; Healey <i>et al.</i> (<i>et al.</i> (2018) ^b
Atherinopsidae	<i>Leuresthes tenuis</i>	California grunion		X	Johnson <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Carangidae	<i>Lichia amia</i>	Leerfish		X	Henriques <i>et al.</i> (2012) ^b
Pleuronectidae	<i>Limanda limanda</i>	Common dab	X		Tysklind <i>et al.</i> (2009); Tysklind <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Pleuronectidae	<i>Limanda punctatissima</i>	Speckled flounder	X		Kim <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^a

Blenniidae	<i>Lipophrys pholis</i>	Shanny		X	Francisco <i>et al.</i> (2006); Francisco <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Sparidae	<i>Lithognathus mormyrus</i>	Sand steenbras	X	X	Sala-Bozano <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^a ; Sala-Bozano <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^b
Lophiidae	<i>Lophius budegassa</i>	Blackbellied angler	X		Blanco <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Lophiidae	<i>Lophius piscatorius</i>	Angler	X		Blanco <i>et al.</i> (2006); Chevolot <i>et al.</i> (2006) ^a
Lutjanidae	<i>Lutjanus analis</i>	Mutton snapper	X	X	Carson <i>et al.</i> (2011); De Souza <i>et al.</i> (2019); Renshaw <i>et al.</i> (2007); Shulzitski (2005)
Lutjanidae	<i>Lutjanus campechanus</i>	Northern red snapper	X		Hollenbeck <i>et al.</i> (2015); Saillant (2003); Saillant & Gold (2006); Saillant <i>et al.</i> (2006); Saillant <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Lutjanidae	<i>Lutjanus carponotatus</i>	Spanish flag snapper	X	X	Evans <i>et al.</i> (2010); Harrison <i>et al.</i> (2014); Veilleux <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Lutjanidae	<i>Lutjanus fulvus</i>	Blacktail snapper		X	Gaither <i>et al.</i> (2010) ^a ; Gaither <i>et al.</i> (2012); Harrison <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Lutjanidae	<i>Lutjanus jocu</i>	Dog snapper		X	De Souza <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Lutjanidae	<i>Lutjanus kasmira</i>	Common bluestripe snapper		X	Gaither <i>et al.</i> (2010) ^a ; Gaither <i>et al.</i> (2010) ^b ; Gaither <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Lutjanidae	<i>Lutjanus peru</i>	Pacific red snapper	X		Munguía-Vega <i>et al.</i> (2018); Paz-García <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Lutjanidae	<i>Lutjanus purpureus</i>	Southern red snapper		X	Gomes <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Lutjanidae	<i>Lutjanus russellii</i>	Russell's snapper	X		Guo <i>et al.</i> (200)

Lutjanidae	<i>Lutjanus synagris</i>	Lane snapper	X	X	Gold 2011 <i>et al.</i> (); Karlsson <i>et al.</i> (2009); Renshaw <i>et al.</i> (2007); Silva <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Sciaenidae	<i>Macrodon ancylodon</i>	King weakfish		X	Santos <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Macrouridae	<i>Macrourus berglax</i>	Roughhead grenadier	X		Coscia <i>et al.</i> (2018); Helyar <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Macruronidae	<i>Macruronus margellanicus</i>	Patagonian grenadier	X		D'Amato <i>et al.</i> (1999); D'Amato (2006); Machado-Schiaffino & Garcia-Vazquez (2011)
Istiophoridae	<i>Makaira nigricans</i>	Blue marlin	X	X	McDowell <i>et al.</i> (2007); Sorenson <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Carangidae	<i>Megalaspis cordyla</i>	Torpedo scad	X		Kempter <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Gadidae	<i>Melanogrammus aeglefinus</i>	Haddock	X		Lage & Kornfield (1999); O'Reilly <i>et al.</i> (2002)
Atherinopsidae	<i>Menidia menidia</i>	Atlantic silverside	X	X	Mach <i>et al.</i> (2011); Sbrocco <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Sciaenidae	<i>Menticirrhus americanus</i>	Southern kingcroaker		X	Freitas <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Gadidae	<i>Merlangius merlangus</i>	Whiting	X	X	Charrier <i>et al.</i> (2007); Eiríksson & Árnason (2014)
Merlucciidae	<i>Merluccius albidus</i>	Offshore silver hake		X	Machado-Schiaffino <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Merlucciidae	<i>Merluccius bilinearis</i>	Silver hake	X	X	Machado-Schiaffino <i>et al.</i> (2010); Machado-Schiaffino <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Merlucciidae	<i>Merluccius capensis</i>	Shallow-water cape hake		X	von der Heyden <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Merlucciidae	<i>Merluccius hubbsi</i>	Argentine hake	X		Machado-Schiaffino <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Merlucciidae	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	European hake	X		Castillo <i>et al.</i> (2005); Lundy <i>et al.</i> (2000);

					Pita <i>et al.</i> (2011); Pita <i>et al.</i> (2016); Tanner <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Merlucciidae	<i>Merluccius paradoxus</i>	Deep-water cape hake		X	von der Heyden <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Merlucciidae	<i>Merluccius productus</i>	North Pacific hake	X		García-De León <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Soleidae	<i>Microchirus azevia</i>	Bastard sole	X		Catanese <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Gadidae	<i>Micromesistius poutassou</i>	Blue whiting	X		Was <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Sciaenidae	<i>Micropogonias furnieri</i>	Whitemouth croaker	X	X	D'Anatro <i>et al.</i> (2011); Periera <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Sciaenidae	<i>Micropogonias undulatus</i>	Atlantic croaker		X	Anderson <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Pleuronectidae	<i>Microstomus pacificus</i>	Dover sole		X	Stepien (1999)
Sciaenidae	<i>Miichthys miiuy</i>	Mi-iuy croaker	X	X	Cheng <i>et al.</i> (2011); Wang <i>et al.</i> (2010) ^c ; Xu <i>et al.</i> (2014); Zhao <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^c
Lotidae	<i>Molva molva</i>	Ling	X		Gonzalez <i>et al.</i> (2015); Ring <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Mullidae	<i>Mulloidichthys flavolineatus</i>	Yellowstripe goatfish	X	X	Fernandez-Silva <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Mullidae	<i>Mullus barbatus barbatus</i>	Red mullet	X		Félix-Hackradt <i>et al.</i> (2013); Galarza <i>et al.</i> (2007) ^b ; Galarza <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^b ; Garoia <i>et al.</i> (2004); Maggio <i>et al.</i> (2009); Matic-Skoko <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Mullidae	<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>	Surmullet	X		Félix-Hackradt <i>et al.</i> (2013); Galarza <i>et al.</i> (2007) ^b ; Galarza <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^a ; Galarza <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^b ; Matic-Skoko <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Triakidae	<i>Mustelus asterias</i>	Starry smooth-hound		X	Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)

Triakidae	<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	Smooth-hound	X	X	Hull <i>et al.</i> (2019); Maduna <i>et al.</i> (2016); Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Triakidae	<i>Mustelus palumbes</i>	Whitespotted smooth-hound	X		Maduna <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Serranidae	<i>Mycteroperca microlepis</i>	Gag	X		Cushman <i>et al.</i> (2009); Jue (2010)
Serranidae	<i>Mycteroperca phenax</i>	Scamp	X		Zatcoff <i>et al.</i> (2004)
Holocentridae	<i>Myripristis berndti</i>	Blotcheye soldierfish		X	Craig <i>et al.</i> (2007); Muths <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Holocentridae	<i>Myripristis jacobus</i>	Blackbar soldierfish		X	Bowen <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Acanthuridae	<i>Naso unicornis</i>	Bluespine unicornfish	X	X	Horne <i>et al.</i> (2010); Horne <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Cheilodactylidae	<i>Nemadactylus macropterus</i>	Tarakihi	X		Burridge & Smolenski (2003)
Pomacentridae	<i>Neopomacentrus filamentosus</i>	Brown demoiselle	X		Jones & Barber (2005)
Sciaenidae	<i>Nibea albiflora</i>	Yellow drum	X		Ma <i>et al.</i> (2011) ^b ; Xing <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^a ; Xu <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Nototheniidae	<i>Notothenia rossii</i>	Marbled rockcod	X		Young <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Nototheniidae	<i>Nototheniops larseni</i>	Painted notie	X		Damerau <i>et al.</i> (2014) ^b
Leiognathidae	<i>Nuchequula mannusella</i>	NA		X	Gao <i>et al.</i> (2019) ^a
Sparidae	<i>Oblada melanura</i>	Saddled seabream	X		Calò <i>et al.</i> (2016); Galarza <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^a
Lutjanidae	<i>Ocyurus chrysurus</i>	Yellowtail snapper	X		Renshaw <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Balistidae	<i>Odonus niger</i>	Red-toothed triggerfish		X	Matias <i>et al.</i> (2013)

Rajidae	<i>Okamejei kenojei</i>	Ocellate spot skate		X	Misawa <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Hexagrammidae	<i>Ophiodon elongatus</i>	Lingcod	X	X (π)	LeClair <i>et al.</i> (2006); Markos <i>et al.</i> (2007); Withler <i>et al.</i> (2003)
Opistognathidae	<i>Opistognathus aurifrons</i>	Yellowhead jawfish		X	Ho <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Oplegnathidae	<i>Oplegnathus fasciatus</i>	Barred knifefish		X	Xiao <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Apogonidae	<i>Ostorhinchus doederleini</i>	Doederlein's cardinalfish	X		Miller-Sims <i>et al.</i> (2004)
Sparidae	<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>	Blackspot seabream	X		Stockley <i>et al.</i> (2005)
Sparidae	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	Common pandora		X	Angiulli <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Nototheniidae	<i>Pagothenia borchgrevinki</i>	Bald notothen	X		Van de Putte <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Sparidae	<i>Pagrus auratus</i>	Silver seabream	X		Bernal-Ramírez <i>et al.</i> (2003); Gardner <i>et al.</i> (2017); Hauser <i>et al.</i> (2002); Le Port <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Sparidae	<i>Pagrus auriga</i>	Redbanded seabream	X		Ponce <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Sparidae	<i>Pagrus major</i>	Red seabream	X	X	Hamasaki <i>et al.</i> (2010); Perez-Enriques & Taniguchi (1999); Shishidou <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Sparidae	<i>Pagrus pagrus</i>	Red porgy	X	X	Ball <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Stromateidae	<i>Pampus argenteus</i>	Silver pomfret	X	X	Peng <i>et al.</i> (2009); Sun <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Stromateidae	<i>Pampus chinensis</i>	Chinese silver pomfret	X	X	Li <i>et al.</i> (2019); Sun & Tang (2018)
Stromateidae	<i>Pampus minor</i>	Southern lesser pomfret		X	Li <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Terarogidae	<i>Paracentropogon</i>	NA	X		Kokita <i>et al.</i> (2006)

	<i>rubripinnis</i>				
Serranidae	<i>Paralabrax albomaculatus</i>	Camotillo	X		Bertolotti <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Serranidae	<i>Paralabrax clathratus</i>	Kelp bass	X		Selkoe <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Seranidae	<i>Paralabrax nebulifer</i>	Barred sand bass	X		Domínguez-Contreras <i>et al.</i> (2018); Paterson <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Paralichthyidae	<i>Paralichthys californicus</i>	California flounder		X	Craig <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Paralichthyidae	<i>Paralichthys olivaceus</i>	Bastard halibut	X	X	Kim <i>et al.</i> (2003); Kim <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^b ; Kim <i>et al.</i> (2010) ^c ; Li <i>et al.</i> (2011); Sekino & Hara (2001); Shigenobu <i>et al.</i> (2007); Takagi <i>et al.</i> (1999) ^a ; Xu <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Haemulidae	<i>Parapristipoma trilineatum</i>	Chicken grunt	X		Kumagai <i>et al.</i> (2004)
Mullidae	<i>Parupeneus multifasciatus</i>	Manybar goatfish		X	Matias <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Sciaenidae	<i>Pennahia argentata</i>	Silver croaker		X	Han <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Pholidae	<i>Pholis fangi</i>	NA		X	Gao <i>et al.</i> (2019) ^b
Mugilidae	<i>Planiliza affinis</i>	Eastern keelback	X		Liu <i>et al.</i> (2019) ^b
Serranidae	<i>Plectropomus areolatus</i>	Squaretail coralgrouper	X		Ma <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Serranidae	<i>Plectropomus leopardus</i>	Leopard coralgroup	X	X	Ding <i>et al.</i> (2009); Herwerden <i>et al.</i> (2009); Ma <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Serranidae	<i>Plectropomus maculatus</i>	Spotted coralgroup		X	Evans <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Nototheniidae	<i>Pleuragramma antarctica</i>	Antarctic silverfish	X	X	Papetti <i>et al.</i> (2011); Zane <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Hexagrammidae	<i>Pleurogrammus</i>	Atka mackerel	X		Spies <i>et al.</i> (2005)

	<i>monopterygius</i>				
Pleuronectidae	<i>Pleuronectes platessa</i>	European plaice	X		Hemmer-Hansen (2007); Hoarau <i>et al.</i> (2002); Hoarau <i>et al.</i> (2004); Was <i>et al.</i> (2010); Watts <i>et al.</i> (1999); Watts <i>et al.</i> (2001); Watts <i>et al.</i> (2004); Watts <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Polyprionidae	<i>Polyprion americanus</i>	Wreckfish	X		Ball <i>et al.</i> (2000)
Polyprionidae	<i>Polyprion oxygeneios</i>	Hapuku wreckfish	X	X	Ball <i>et al.</i> (2000); Lane <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Pomacentridae	<i>Pomacentrus amboinensis</i>	Ambon damsel	X		Jones <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Pomacentridae	<i>Pomacentrus coelestis</i>	Neon damselfish	X	X	Frédérich <i>et al.</i> (2012); Liu <i>et al.</i> (2010) ^b ; Liu <i>et al.</i> (2012); Miller-Sims <i>et al.</i> (2005) ^b
Pomacentridae	<i>Pomacentrus moluccensis</i>	Lemon damsel		X (π)	Drew <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Pomatomidae	<i>Pomatomus saltatrix</i>	Bluefish	X		Dos Santos <i>et al.</i> (2008); Miralles <i>et al.</i> (2014); Reid <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Gobiidae	<i>Pomatoschistus marmoratus</i>	Marbled goby	X		Berrebi <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Scorpaenidae	<i>Pontinus kuhlii</i>	Offshore rockfish		X	Catarino <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Carcharhinidae	<i>Prionace glauca</i>	Blue shark		X	Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Lutjanidae	<i>Pristipomoides filamentosus</i>	Crimson jobfish	X	X	Gaither <i>et al.</i> (2011) ^b ; Mzingirwa <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Lutjanidae	<i>Pristipomoides zonatus</i>	Oblique-banded snapper		X	Kennington <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Sciaenidae	<i>Protonibea diacanthus</i>	Blackspotted croaker	X		Taillebois <i>et al.</i> (2017)

Pleuronectidae	<i>Pseudopleuronectes americanus</i>	Winter flounder	X		Crivello <i>et al.</i> (2004); McClelland <i>et al.</i> (2005)
Pleuronectidae	<i>Pseudopleuronectes herzensteini</i>	Yellow striped flounder	X	X	Kim <i>et al.</i> (2007); Kim <i>et al.</i> (2010) ^d
Pleuronectidae	<i>Pseudopleuronectes yokohamae</i>	Marbled flounder	X	X (<i>H_d</i>)	Kim <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^b ; Kitanishi <i>et al.</i> (2014); Lee <i>et al.</i> (2012); Sato <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Apogonidae	<i>Pterapogon kauderni</i>	Banggai cardinalfish	X		Hoffman <i>et al.</i> (2004); Hoffman <i>et al.</i> (2005)
Gobiidae	<i>Pterogobius elapoides</i>	NA	X		Nohara <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^b
Gobiidae	<i>Pterogobius zonoleucus</i>	NA	X		Nohara <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^b
Scorpaenidae	<i>Pterois miles</i>	Devil firefish		X	Kochzius & Blohm (2005)
Rachycentridae	<i>Rachycentron canadum</i>	Cobia	X		Divya <i>et al.</i> (2019); Phinchongsakuldit <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Rajidae	<i>Raja clavata</i>	Thornback ray	X	X	Chevolot <i>et al.</i> (2005); Chevolot <i>et al.</i> (2006) ^a ; Chevolot <i>et al.</i> (2006) ^b ; Ferrari <i>et al.</i> (2018); Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Rajidae	<i>Raja miraletus</i>	Brown ray		X	Ferrari <i>et al.</i> (2018); Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Rajidae	<i>Raja polystigma</i>	Speckled ray		X	Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Rajidae	<i>Raja radula</i>	Rough ray		X	Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Scombridae	<i>Rastrelliger kanagartha</i>	Indian mackerel		X	Akib <i>et al.</i> (2015); Pedrosa-Gerasmio <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Pleuronectidae	<i>Reinhardtius hippoglossoides</i>	Greenland halibut		X	Vis <i>et al.</i> (1997)

Rhincodontidae	<i>Rinchodon typus</i>	Whale shark	X	X	Vignaud <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Carcharhinidae	<i>Rhizoprionodon acutus</i>	Milk shark		X	Ovenden <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Lutjanidae	<i>Rhomboplites aurorubens</i>	Vermilion snapper	X		Bagley & Geller (1998); Bagley <i>et al.</i> (1999)
Tripterygiidae	<i>Ruanoho whero</i>	Spectacled triplefin		X	Hickey <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Scombridae	<i>Sarda sarda</i>	Atlantic bonito	X		Turan (2015)
Clupeidae	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	European pilchard	X		Gonzalez & Zardoya (2007); Ruggeri <i>et al.</i> (2012); Ruggeri <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Clupeidae	<i>Sardinella lemuru</i>	Bali sardinella		X	Pedrosa-Gerasmio <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Clupeidae	<i>Sardinella longiceps</i>	Indian oil sardine	X		Sebastian <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Clupeidae	<i>Sardinops sagax</i>	South American pilchard		X	Bowen & Grant (1997); García-Rodríguez <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Synodontidae	<i>Saurida elongata</i>	Slender lizardfish		X	Tu <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Blenniidae	<i>Scartella cristata</i>	Molly miller	X		Mackiewicz <i>et al.</i> (2005)
Scaridae	<i>Scarus ghobban</i>	Blue-barred parrotfish		X	Visram <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Scaridae	<i>Scarus psittacus</i>	Common parrotfish		X	Winters <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Sciaenidae	<i>Sciaenops ocellatus</i>	Red drum	X		Chapman <i>et al.</i> (2002); Karlsson <i>et al.</i> (2008) ^a ; Karlsson <i>et al.</i> (2008) ^b ; Turner <i>et al.</i> (1998)
Scombridae	<i>Scomber australasicus</i>	Blue mackerel	X	X	Scoles <i>et al.</i> (1989); Tang <i>et al.</i> (2009); Tzeng <i>et al.</i> (2007); Yagashita & Kobayashi (2008)

Scombridae	<i>Scomber japonicus</i>	Chub mackerel	X	X	Cha <i>et al.</i> (2010); Cheng <i>et al.</i> (2014); Cheng <i>et al.</i> (2015); Scoles <i>et al.</i> (1998); Tzeng <i>et al.</i> (2007); Yagashita & Kobayashi (2008)
Scombridae	<i>Scomber scombrus</i>	Atlantic mackerel	X	X	de Souza <i>et al.</i> (2006); Scoles <i>et al.</i> (1998); Papetti <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Scombridae	<i>Scomberomorus brasiliensis</i>	Serra Spanish mackerel	X	X	Gold <i>et al.</i> (2010); Renshaw <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^b
Scombridae	<i>Scomberomorus cavalla</i>	King mackerel		X	Santa Brígida <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Scombridae	<i>Scomberomorus commerson</i>	Narrow-barred Spanish mackerel	X	X	Fauvleot & Borso (2011) Hoolihan <i>et al.</i> (2006); Radhakrishnan <i>et al.</i> (2018); van Herwerden <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Scombridae	<i>Scomberomorus concolor</i>	Monterey Spanish mackerel	X	X	Magallón-Gayón <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Scombridae	<i>Scomberomorus niphonius</i>	Japanese Spanish mackerel	X	X	Shui <i>et al.</i> (2009); Nakajima <i>et al.</i> (2014); Xing <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^b ; Yokoyama <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Scombridae	<i>Scomberomorus semifasciatus</i>	Broad-barred king mackerel		X	Broderick <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Scombridae	<i>Scomberomorus sierra</i>	Pacific sierra		X	López <i>et al.</i> (2010) ^b
Scombropidae	<i>Scombrops boops</i>	Gnomefish		X	Noguchi <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Scombropidae	<i>Scombrops gilberti</i>	NA		X	Itoi <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Scophthalmidae	<i>Scophthalmus maximus</i>	Turbot	X		Bouza <i>et al.</i> (2002); Florin & Höglund (2007); Nielsen <i>et al.</i> (2004); Pardo <i>et al.</i> (2005); Vilas <i>et al.</i> (2015)

Scophthalmidae	<i>Scophthalmus rhombus</i>	Brill	X		Bouza <i>et al.</i> (2002)
Scyliorhinidae	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	Small-spotted catshark	X	X	Ferrari <i>et al.</i> (2018); Kousteni <i>et al.</i> (2015); Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Scyliorhinidae	<i>Scyliorhinus stellaris</i>	Nursehound		X	Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes alutus</i>	Pacific ocean perch	X		Palof <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes atrovirens</i>	Kelp rockfish	X		Gilbert-Horvath <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes auriculatus</i>	Brown rockfish	X		Buonaccorsi <i>et al.</i> (2005); Hauser <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes borealis</i>	Shortraker rockfish	X		Matala <i>et al.</i> (2004) ^a
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes caurinus</i>	Copper rockfish	X		Buonaccorsi <i>et al.</i> (2002)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes crameri</i>	Darkblotched rockfish	X		Gomez-Uchida & Banks (2005)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes emphaeus</i>	Puget Sound rockfish		X (π)	Sitka <i>et al.</i> (2005)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes fasciatus</i>	Acadian redfish	X		Pampoulie & Daniélsdóttir (2008); Roques <i>et al.</i> (1999); Roques <i>et al.</i> (2001); Schmidt (2005); Valentin <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes flavidus</i>	Yellowtail rockfish	X	X	Hess <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes helvomaculatus</i>	Rosethorn rockfish		X	Rocha-Olivares & Vetter (1999)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes inermis</i>	Dark-banded rockfish	X		An <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^a ; Gonzalez <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes macdonaldi</i>	Mexican rockfish	X		Rocha-Olivares & Sandoval-Castillo (2003)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes melanops</i>	Black rockfish	X		Lotterhos & Markel (2012); Lotterhos 2014); Miller <i>et al.</i> (2005)

Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes mentella</i>	Beaked redfish	X		Pampoulie & Daniélsdóttir (2008); Roques <i>et al.</i> (1999); Roques <i>et al.</i> (2001); Schmidt (2005); Stefánsson <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^a ; Stefánsson <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^b ; Valentin <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes miniatus</i>	Vermilion rockfish		X	Hyde & Vetter (2009)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes mystinus</i>	Blue rockfish	X		Burford & Larson (2007); Burford & Bernardi (2008); Burford (2009)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes norvegicus</i>	Golden redfish	X		Pampoulie & Daniélsdóttir (2008); Pampoulie <i>et al.</i> (2009); Roques <i>et al.</i> (1999); Schmidt (2005)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes oculatus</i>	Patagonian redfish		X	Nuñez <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes paucispinis</i>	Bocaccio rockfish	X		Matala <i>et al.</i> (2004) ^b
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes pinniger</i>	Canary rockfish	X		Gomez-Uchida (2006); Hyde <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes polyspinus</i>	Northern rockfish	X		Gharret <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes rastrelliger</i>	Grass rockfish	X		Buonaccorsi <i>et al.</i> (2004); Westerman <i>et al.</i> (2005)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes ruberrimus</i>	Yelloweye rockfish	X		Siegle <i>et al.</i> (2013); Yamanaka & Lacko (2001)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes schlegelii</i>	Korean rockfish	X	X	An <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^b ; An <i>et al.</i> (2012) ^b ; Gao <i>et al.</i> (2016); Yoshida <i>et al.</i> (2005); Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2014) ^b
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes thompsoni</i>	Goldeye rockfish	X		Sekino & Hara (2001)
Sebastidae	<i>Sebastes viviparus</i>	Norway redfish	X		Pampoulie & Daniélsdóttir (2008); Roques <i>et al.</i> (1999)

Scorpaenidae	<i>Sebastiscus marmoratus</i>	False kelpfish	X	X	Deng <i>et al.</i> (2015); Li <i>et al.</i> (2014) ^a ; Liu <i>et al.</i> (2019) ^c ; Yin <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Carangidae	<i>Selar crumenophthalmus</i>	Bigeye scad		X	Pedrosa-Gerasmio <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Labridae	<i>Semicossyphus darwini</i>	Galápagos sheephead wrasse	X		Poortvliet <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Labridae	<i>Semicossyphus pulcher</i>	California sheephead	X		Poortvliet <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Carangidae	<i>Seriola dumerili</i>	Greater amberjack	X	X (<i>H_d</i>)	Babbucci <i>et al.</i> (2006); Renshaw <i>et al.</i> (2006); Šegvić-Bubić <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Carangidae	<i>Seriola lalandi</i>	Yellowtail amberjack	X	X	Nugruho <i>et al.</i> (2001); Sepúlveda & González (2017)
Carangidae	<i>Seriola rivoliana</i>	Longfin yellowtail		X (<i>H_d</i>)	Šegvić-Bubić <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Centrolophidae	<i>Seriolella brama</i>	Common warehou		X	Robinson <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Serranidae	<i>Serranus cabrilla</i>	Comber	X		Carreras-Carbonell <i>et al.</i> (2006); Galarza <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^a ; Schunter <i>et al.</i> (2011) ^b
Centrolophidae	<i>Seriolella punctata</i>	Silver warehou		X	Robinson <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Siganidae	<i>Siganus fuscescens</i>	Mottled spinefoot	X	X	Li <i>et al.</i> (2013) ^c ; Ravago-Gotanco <i>et al.</i> (2010); Ravago-Gotanco & Junio-Meñez (2010); Ravago-Gotanco <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Siganidae	<i>Siganus guttatus</i>	Orange-spotted spinefoot		X	Iwamoto <i>et al.</i> (2009); Iwamoto <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Siganidae	<i>Siganus spinus</i>	Little spinefoot	X	X	Iwamoto <i>et al.</i> (2009); Priest <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Sillaginidae	<i>Sillago japonica</i>	Japanese sillago	X	X	Gao <i>et al.</i> (2019) ^c ; Ueno <i>et al.</i> (2013); Umino <i>et al.</i> (2013)

Sillaginidae	<i>Sillago parvisquamis</i>	Small-scale sillago	X		Ueno <i>et al.</i> (2013); Umino <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Apogonidae	<i>Siphamia tubifer</i>	Tubifer cardinalfish	X		Alpermann <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Soleidae	<i>Solea senegalensis</i>	Senegalese sole	X		Díaz-Ferguson <i>et al.</i> (2012); Funes <i>et al.</i> (2004)
Soleidae	<i>Solea solea</i>	Common sole	X	X	Cuveliers <i>et al.</i> (2011); Cuveliers <i>et al.</i> (2012); Garoia <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Somniosidae	<i>Somniosus rostratus</i>	Little sleeper shark		X	Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Sparidae	<i>Sparus aurata</i>	Gilthead seabream	X	X	Alarcón <i>et al.</i> (2004); Chaoui <i>et al.</i> (2012); Coscia <i>et al.</i> (2012); De Innocentiis <i>et al.</i> (2004); Franchini <i>et al.</i> (2012); Karaiskou <i>et al.</i> (2009); Šegvić-Bubić <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Apogonidae	<i>Sphaeramia orbicularis</i>	Orbiculate cardinalfish		X	Gotoh <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Sphyraenidae	<i>Sphyraena barracuda</i>	Great barracuda		X	Daly-Engel <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Sphyraenidae	<i>Sphyraena viridensis</i>	Yellowmouth barracuda		X (<i>H_d</i>)	Milana <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Sphyrnidae	<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>	Scalloped hammerhead	X	X	Castillo-Olguín <i>et al.</i> (2012); Duncan <i>et al.</i> (2006); Nance <i>et al.</i> (2011); Ovenden <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Gasterosteidae	<i>Spinachia spinachia</i>	Sea stickleback	X		Jones <i>et al.</i> (1998) ^b
Clupeidae	<i>Sprattus fuegensis</i>	Falkland sprat	X		Canales-Aguirre <i>et al.</i> (2016); Ferrada-Fuentes <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Clupeidae	<i>Sprattus sprattus</i>	European sprat	X	X	Debes <i>et al.</i> (2008); Dailianis <i>et al.</i> (2008); Glover <i>et al.</i> (2011); Limborg <i>et</i>

					<i>al.</i> (2009); Limborg <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Squalidae	<i>Squalus acanthias</i>	Picked dogfish	X		McCauley <i>et al.</i> (2004); Thorburn <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Squalidae	<i>Squalus blainville</i>	Longnose spurdog	X	X	Kousteni <i>et al.</i> (2016); Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Pomacentridae	<i>Stegastes partitus</i>	Bicolor damselfish	X		Hepburn <i>et al.</i> (2009); Purcell <i>et al.</i> (2009); Pusack <i>et al.</i> (2014); Salas <i>et al.</i> (2010); Williams <i>et al.</i> (2003)
Myctophidae	<i>Stenobrachius leucopsarus</i>	Northern lampfish		X	Kojima <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Myctophidae	<i>Stenobrachius nannochir</i>	Giant lanternfish		X	Kojima <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Monacanthidae	<i>Stephanolepis cirrhifer</i>	Threadsail filefish	X		An <i>et al.</i> (2011); An <i>et al.</i> (2013) ^a
Labridae	<i>Symphodus melops</i>	Corkwing wrasse	X		Knutsen <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Labridae	<i>Symphodus tinca</i>	East Atlantic peacock wrasse	X		Galarza <i>et al.</i> (2006); Galarza <i>et al.</i> (2009) ^a
Syngnathidae	<i>Syngnathus auliscus</i>	Barred pipefish	X		Wilson (2006)
Syngnathidae	<i>Syngnathus floridae</i>	Dusky pipefish	X		Mobley <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Syngnathidae	<i>Syngnathus leptorhynchus</i>	Bay pipefish		X	Wilson (2006)
Syngnathidae	<i>Syngnathus scovelli</i>	Gulf pipefish	X		Jones & Avise (1997)
Syngnathidae	<i>Syngnathus typhle</i>	Broadnosed pipefish	X		Jones <i>et al.</i> (1999)
Tetraodontidae	<i>Takifugu rubripes</i>	Japanese pufferfish		X	Reza <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Labridae	<i>Thalassoma bifasciatum</i>	Bluehead	X	X	Haney <i>et al.</i> (2007); Purcell <i>et al.</i> (2006); Williams <i>et al.</i> (2004) ^b
Monacanthidae	<i>Thamnaconus</i>	Leser-spotted		X	Li <i>et al.</i> (2014) ^b

	<i>hypargyreus</i>	leatherjacket			
Monacanthidae	<i>Thamnaconus modestus</i>	Black scraper	X		An <i>et al.</i> (2013) ^b
Monacanthidae	<i>Thamnaconus septentrionalis</i>	Greenfin horse-faced filefish	X		Xu <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Scombridae	<i>Thunnus alalunga</i>	Albacore	X		Davies <i>et al.</i> (2011); Montes <i>et al.</i> (2012); Takagi <i>et al.</i> (1999) ^b ; Takagi <i>et al.</i> (2001)
Scombridae	<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Yellowfin tuna	X	X	Aguila <i>et al.</i> (2015); Dammannagoda <i>et al.</i> (2008); Diaz-Jaimes & Uribe-Alcocer (2006); Kunal <i>et al.</i> (2013); Qiu & Miyamoto (2011); Takagi <i>et al.</i> (1999) ^b
Scombridae	<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	Bigeye tuna	X	X	Durand <i>et al.</i> (2005); Gonzalez <i>et al.</i> (2008); Takagi <i>et al.</i> (1999) ^b ; Wu <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Scombridae	<i>Thunnus orientalis</i>	Pacific bluefin tuna	X		Morishima <i>et al.</i> (2009); Qiu & Miyamoto (2011); Takagi <i>et al.</i> (1999) ^b
Scombridae	<i>Thunnus thynnus</i>	Atlantic bluefin tuna	X		Riccioni <i>et al.</i> (2010); Takagi <i>et al.</i> (1999) ^b ; Vella <i>et al.</i> (2009); Vella <i>et al.</i> (2016); Viñas <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Torpedinidae	<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	Marbled electric ray		X	Vella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Sciaenidae	<i>Totoaba macdonaldi</i>	Totoaba	X	X	Valenzuela-Quiñonez <i>et al.</i> (2014); Valenzuela-Quiñonez <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Plesiopidae	<i>Trachinops caudimaculatus</i>	Southern hulafish	X		McWilliam <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Carangidae	<i>Trachinotus carolinus</i>	Florida pompano	X		Seyoum <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Carangidae	<i>Trachinotus falcatus</i>	Permit	X		Seyoum <i>et al.</i> (2007)

Carangidae	<i>Trachinotus goodei</i>	Great pompano	X		Seyoum <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Carangidae	<i>Trachurus japonicus</i>	Japanese jack mackerel	X		Chang <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Carangidae	<i>Trachurus mediterraneus</i>	Mediterranean horse mackerel		X	Bektas & Belduz (2008)
Carangidae	<i>Trachurus murphyi</i>	Chilean jack mackerel	X	X	Canales-Aguirre <i>et al.</i> (2010); Cárdenas <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Carangidae	<i>Trachurus picturatus</i>	Blue jack mackerel		X	Bektas & Belduz (2008)
Carangidae	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	Atlantic horse mackerel	X	X	Bektas & Belduz (2008); Kasapidis & Magoulas (2008)
Nototheniidae	<i>Trematomus bernacchii</i>	Emerald rockcod	X		Van de Putte <i>et al.</i> (2009); Van de Putte <i>et al.</i> (2012) ^b
Nototheniidae	<i>Trematomus eulepidotus</i>	Blunt scalyhead	X		Damerau <i>et al.</i> (2012); Van de Putte <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Nototheniidae	<i>Trematomus hansonii</i>	Striped rockcod	X		Van de Putte <i>et al.</i> (2009); Van de Putte <i>et al.</i> (2012) ^b
Nototheniidae	<i>Trematomus newnesi</i>	Dusky rockcod	X		Damerau <i>et al.</i> (2012); Van de Putte <i>et al.</i> (2009); Van de Putte <i>et al.</i> (2012) ^b ; Van Houdt <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Nototheniidae	<i>Trematomus scotti</i>	Crowned rockcod	X		Van de Putte <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Carcharhinidae	<i>Triaenodon obesus</i>	Whitetip reef shark		X	Whitney <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Triakidae	<i>Triakis megalopterus</i>	Sharptooth houndshark	X		Maduna <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Tripterygiidae	<i>Tripterygion delais</i>	Black-faced blenny	X		Carreras-Carbonell <i>et al.</i> (2004); Galarza

					<i>et al.</i> (2009) ^a
Rhinobatidae	<i>Trygonorrhina dumerilii</i>	Sothorn fiddler ray		X (<i>H_d</i>)	Donnellan <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Rhinobatidae	<i>Trygonorrhina fasciata</i>	Eastern fiddler ray		X (<i>H_d</i>)	Donnellan <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Urotrygonidae	<i>Urobatis helleri</i>	Haller's round ray	X		Plank <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Phycidae	<i>Urophycis tenuis</i>	White hake	X		Bradbury <i>et al.</i> (2009); Roy <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Muraenidae	<i>Uropterygius micropterus</i>	Tidepool snake moray		X	Huang <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Pleuronectidae	<i>Verasper moseri</i>	Barfin flounder	X		Ma & Chen (2009); Miao <i>et al.</i> (2009); Ortega-Villaizán Romo <i>et al.</i> (2003); Ortega-Villaizán Romo <i>et al.</i> (2006) ^a ; Ortega-Villaizán Romo <i>et al.</i> (2006) ^b
Pleuronectidae	<i>Verasper variegatus</i>	Spotted halibut	X	X	Ortega-Villaizán Romo <i>et al.</i> (2006) ^a ; Ortega-Villaizán Romo <i>et al.</i> (2006) ^b ; Sekino <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Xiphiidae	<i>Xiphias gladius</i>	Swordfish		X	Alvarado Bremer <i>et al.</i> (2005); Muths <i>et al.</i> (2005)
Labridae	<i>Xyrichtys novacula</i>	Pearly razorfish		X (<i>H_d</i>)	Nirchio <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Rajidae	<i>Zearaja chilensis</i>	Yellownose skate	X	X	Vargas-Caro <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Rajidae	<i>Zearaja maugeana</i>	Maugean skate	X		Weltz <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Acanthuridae	<i>Zebrasoma flavescens</i>	Yellow tang		X	Eble <i>et al.</i> (2011) ^b
Zoarcidae	<i>Zoarces viviparus</i>	Viviparous eelpout	X		Kinitz <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Gobiidae	<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	Grass goby	X		Bisol <i>et al.</i> (2007)

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